

Evaluation of Asian gall midge (AGM)-resistant varieties for the African rice gall midge (ARGM)

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We screened 88 AGM-resistant varieties for the ARGM *Orseolia oryzivora* Harris and Gagne, a major insect pest of lowland rice in Nigeria. The trial was carried out under field conditions at NCRI during the 1989 wet season. Seedlings were transplanted 21 d after seeding at 20- × 20-cm spacing in one

20-hill row/entry, replicated twice. ARGM damage was scored at 45 d after transplanting (DT).

Twenty-four of the 88 entries were rated highly to moderately resistant (see table).

Nineteen of the resistant entries and a set of 11 AGM-resistant varieties were screened in the screenhouse during the 1991 wet season. Susceptible variety FARO 37 was grown in half of the screenhouse. We released hundreds of ARGM adults, reared from young galls collected from field-infested plots, in the screenhouse for 2 wk (from 7 d after treatment [DAT]). When the test entries were transplanted at 60 DAT, infestation level was 30.2% on FARO 37. The test entries were planted as in the field with four replications, in the other half of the

screenhouse. ARGM damage was scored at 45 DAT.

Only Aganni and NHTA 8 were moderately resistant. All other entries showed susceptible reactions (see table). □

Screening for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in rice germplasm in Hunan, China

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We screened 4,261 and 3,477 germplasm accessions, respectively, for resistance to BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål and WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath). TN1, Mudgo, and N22 were the susceptible and resistant checks.

We sowed the seed in wooden seedboxes in the greenhouse during 1986-91. Each seedling was infested at the 3- and 4-leaf stage with seven to eight 2d-instar nymphs. Damage was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

One hundred eighty-one germplasm accessions were resistant to BPH, 236 to WBPH, and 18 to both BPH and WBPH (see table). These accessions can be used in breeding programs. □

Resistance of Hunan rice germplasm to BPH and WBPH. China, 1986-91.

Accession no.	Cultivar	Damage score ^a	
		BPH	WBPH
1437	Xiang Zhan	5	5
1653	Huang Yang Zhan	5	5
2064	Xiong Gui Yang	5	5
2068	Long Tan Zhan	5	5
2702	Da Yi Su	5	5
2738	Liu Er Ma	3	5
2739	Hong Mi Mao Zhan	5	5
2743	Er Hao He	3	5
2781	Huang Pi Nuo	5	5
2784	Hong He Nuo	1	3
2793	Bai Mi Nan Yue Zhan	5	3
2910	Da Shui Zhan	5	5
4032	Jiang Xi Zao	1	5
6795	Bai Mi Nuo	5	5
7015	HA79317-4	3	5
7016	HA79317-7	3	3
7207	Guang San Nuo	3	5
A384	Xiang Kang 32-5	3	5
	TN1	9	9
	N22	7	3
	Mudgo	1	-

Reaction^a of Asian GM-resistant varieties to the ARGM. Badeggi, Nigeria.

Variety	Infestation				Origin
	Field (1989)		Screenhouse (1991)		
	%	Score	%	Score	
ARC5848	0.0	HR	18.8	S	India
ARC5911	0.0	HR	10.9	S	India
ARC5984	0.0	HR	14.5	S	India
ARC6015	0.0	HR	11.3	S	India
ARC6087	0.0	HR	9.7	MS	India
ARC6607	0.0	HR	7.7	MS	India
ARC7255	0.0	HR	12.5	S	India
ARC7316	0.0	HR	9.9	MS	India
ARC7317	0.0	HR	21.4	S	India
ARC10272	0.0	HR	12.5	S	India
ARC11074	0.0	HR	7.6	MS	India
ARC11210	0.0	HR	16.4	S	India
ARC13564	0.0	HR	11.8	S	India
PTB19	0.0	HR	10.0	S	India
AC1423	4.8	MR	-	-	India
ARC6618	2.9	MR	8.0	MS	India
ARC7329	2.8	MR	-	-	India
ARC10331	3.4	MR	-	-	India
ARC10660	4.3	MR	12.0	S	India
ARC13902	2.4	MR	-	-	India
ARC15159	3.0	MR	12.2	S	India
ARC18596	2.9	MR	13.3	S	India
PTB28	2.6	MR	7.9	MS	India
Muey Nawng 62 M	3.0	MR	-	-	Thailand
Cisadane	-	-	15.7	S	Indonesia
ARC6157	-	-	15.2	S	India
Kaljira	-	-	14.6	S	Bangladesh
Phodum	-	-	16.4	S	India
OR143-7	-	-	18.8	S	India
Aganni	-	-	4.9	MR	Not known
Parakulan	-	-	6.2	MS	Not known
NHTA8	-	-	4.3	MR	Not known
Chekhalopoiretal	-	-	11.3	S	Not known
CR57-MR1523	-	-	14.5	S	India
OB677	-	-	29.3	HS	Sri Lanka
FARO 37 (susceptible check)	26.4	HS	46.7	HS	IITA, Nigeria

^aScore based on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* where HR = highly resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, and HS = highly susceptible.

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.